

MODE I INTERLAMINAR FAILURE OF STITCHED TEXTILE COMPOSITES MATERIALS. PROPOSITION OF PREDICTIVE REINFORCEMENT MODEL.

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ABSTRACT

The main goal of the through-the-thickness reinforcement in composite materials is to increase their interlaminar resistance.

This paper offers to study the Mode I interlaminar fracture of stitched composites and highlight the effect of the stitching steps and their mechanical properties. In absence of specific method for Mode I energy determination of 3D composite materials, an experimental methodology based on compliance method and taking account the composites mechanical behaviour is proposed.

It was found that mechanical properties and stitching step have a great influence on the Mode I energy values.

At last, a predictive model of Mode I strain energy release rate was adapted from Pigott's works to this materials. The confrontation of experimental and theoretical results indicated a good correlation.

INTRODUCTION

In order to enhance the interlaminar fracture toughness of composites materials, a reinforcement through the thickness was introduced. With weaving technical development, many types of reinforcements in this third direction give rise to composites families called 3D orthogonal composites, stitched composites, interlock etc. ... Among these works, we can mention those of Huang and Col.[1], Mignery and Col. [2] , Guénon and Col. [3] and Dransfeld's review[4] about stitching composites materials.

The diversity and the complexity of the three dimensional structures make their study particularly complicated. In the present state of things, no specific methodology to determine failure energy of these materials has been clearly established.

The few works carried out on interlaminar failure of three dimensional composites materials are based on classical methods applied to 2D composites.

However, Byun and Col [5] used both area and compliance method to measure the Mode I strain energy release rate of 3D orthogonal graphite/epoxy. The authors have concluded that the area method is more adequate than the compliance method.

Nevertheless, the area method which needs the loading and unloading of the specimen, presents some disadvantage.

During the unloading, the pulled-out yarns do not resume their initial locations and therefore progressively undergo compressive stresses which lead to a non linear unloading behaviour and a permanent deflection of the specimen after zero load reached. Some assumptions have been made by the authors in order to apply this method.

In addition, the great instability occurring when the yarns debonds make difficult the experimental measure of the crack length increment.

In this paper, an experimental methodology based on the compliance method and taking into account the material's behaviour is proposed to determine the Mode I energy release rate of stitch composites.

It allows us also, by a correlation with acoustic emission monitoring and microscopic observations to analyse the damage phenomena and to explain the shape of the loading curves obtained for different materials.

Finally, a Mode I failure predictive model based on Pigott's works was applied to these materials.

MATERIAL PRESENTATION

Five different materials obtained by RTM (Resin Transfer Molding) process have been tested. The stitched composites differ by the density and the mechanical properties of the stitch.

The basic weave is a 5HS made with T300 graphite fibre and RTM 6 Matrix. The materials used in this study are summarized in the following table 1.

Reference	Fabric used in the composite	Stitch	Thickness	Stitch step
A	T300/RTM6	T900	6 mm	5 x 5 mm
B1	T300/RTM6	T900	3 mm	7 x 7 mm
B2	T300/RTM6	T900	6 mm	7 x 7 mm
C	T300/RTM6	T300	6 mm	5 x 5 mm
D	T300/RTM6	-----	3 mm	-----

Table 1 : Characteristics of the different materials

The materials A, B1 and B2 are stitched by the same graphite T900 yarn else the stitch used in material C is the T300 graphite.

The unstitched 2D composite called material D was utilised as a reference.

MODE I INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE TOUGHNESS

Experimental procedure:

The specimen used for the Mode I interlaminar test is the Double Cantilever beam (DCB). Each specimen was instrumented with an acoustic emission receptor and strain-gage at the crack tip. The mechanical tests were carried out at a cross head speed of 2 mm/min. An average of 6 or 7 specimens by material was tested with a crack length varied between 25 and 60 mm.

An acquisition system permitted the simultaneous recording of load, displacement, response of strain gage and acoustic emission [AE] signal.

The crack growth mechanisms were observed by means of a travelling optical microscope along the specimen side.

Discussion on the shape load-displacement curves:

The experimental results show two kinds of load-displacement curve. The first one is specific to materials A, B2 and C else the second is typical of material B1.

The difference in the load-displacement curves can be explained by the location of the first row of stitches with respect to that of the pre-crack. This distance is 15 mm for the materials A and B2, 20 mm for the material C and only 5 mm for the material B1.

The next figure shows the first kind of load-deflection curves specific to materials A, B2 and C.

Figure 1 : First kind of load-displacement curve. Material A

The load curve presents first a linear load increase followed by crack initiation in the unstitched portion (2D composites) confirmed by optical microscopy. Then there is another load increase where the row of stitches are loaded.

The strong instability indicates the stitch failure. The number failed stitches is a function of the crack length and consequently it varied during the delamination process.

The interpretation of the AE and deformation curves, correlated with microscopic observations and AE amplitude distribution [6], has permitted to illustrate the failure process and to explain the load-displacement curve.

Figure 2 : Mode I delamination of stitched composite schematising. Correlation with the load-displacement curve.

1- Elastic area. Loading of the unstitched portion "2D composite". Importance of the first stitching row location with respect to the pre-crack.

2- Delamination of the "2D composite".

3- Loading of the first stitching row.

4- First stitch failure. Strong instability.

5- Area with little acoustic emission activity due to the damage established by the first stitch failure.

6- Loading of the following row of stitches.

Contrary to the three precedent materials, the composite B1 presents a linear load increase until the instability (stitch failure) with a little unhooking of the load indicating the crack onset in the unstitched portion "2D composite".

Figure 3 : second kind of load-displacement curve . Composite B1

This behaviour is attributed to the fact that stitches are subjected to the stress from the beginning of the mechanical test. The crack propagation in the unstitched portion is practically non-existent.

The failure modes of this material remain the same compared to the precedent materials with a little difference. The tests on this materials have shown a larger instability than the precedent material, and the macroscopic observations proved that there is more stitching row failure. This phenomenon can be attributed to the thickness effect.

Data reduction :

The strain energy release rate is determined by Irwin's - Kies relation :

$$GI = \frac{1}{2} \frac{P^2}{B} \frac{dC}{da} \tag{1}$$

C : material compliance
B : specimen width

P: Critical load
a : crack length.

The compliance is measured experimentally and plotted against crack length [7]

$$C = \frac{a^n}{h} \tag{2}$$

Where "n" and "h" are materials parameters taking into account the rotation and the shear displacement produced at the crack tip. Then, the value of interlaminar fracture energy depends on the compliance expression and the load at the crack initiation.

Two values of energy will be determined :

- The first one, at crack initiation of the unstitched portion where the compliance used is measured at the beginning of the load-displacement curve.

- The second one, at the stitch failure. Here, the problem is the compliance measurement.

There are two possibilities:

1- To use the compliance in the part "2-3" shown on Fig. 4 and then to consider that the stitches are directly stressed. The initial damage is neglected.

2- To use the compliance from the point "0" to the maximal load (point 3). This compliance will take into account all the damage process from the beginning of the load curve.

The second method will be more adequate than the first one. Nevertheless, we will use the two method and a comparison of results will be done.

Figure 4 : Choice of compliance measurement

Strain Energy release rate at crack initiation in the unstitched portion " 2D composite" :

The Figure 5 shows that the composites A, B1 and C present the same value of energies but 20% higher than the composite D or B1.

Figure 5 : Evolution of "2D composite" energy for the different materials

This difference for the material B1 could be explained by the proximity of the stitch with respect to the crack tip. Thus an early damage localised at the stitch can provide a delamination onset at a low load corresponding to low interlaminar toughness.

Energy release rate at the stitch failure :

The histogram of Figure 6 indicates the values of the energy obtained by both methods. The results exhibit a considerable difference between the two approaches especially for the materials B2 and C. In fact, the first method which does not take into account the damage produced by in the unstitched portion, overestimates the failure energy.

The second method which include the damage entirely is more reliable, all the more than the energy value of the material B1 and B2 are practically the same.

Figure 6 : evolution of energy at the stitch failure for the different materials.

With regard to materials performances, it appears that the material A with a T900 stitch and a 5 mm step offer the best results.

The step's difference (5 mm for composite A and 7 mm for composites B) increase the delamination toughness by about 20 %. The influence of the stitch nature is more significant, thus for the same stitching step, the toughness with T900 yarn is 56 % higher than those of composite C with T300 stitch.

PREDICTIVE MODEL

To built a model from beam theory to determine the critical failure load requires to know the number of row of stitch that are loaded for a given the crack length, which is difficult[5].

We will then solve the problem by energy consideration. For that we will use Pigott's model [8] on continuous fibre debonding and failure in the case of perpendicular crack to the fibre direction. This energy is given by :

$$G = \frac{V_f d \sigma_u^3}{6E_f \tau_i} \quad (3)$$

V_f : Fibre volume fraction
 d : Fibre diameter
 τ_i : Interfacial stress.

σ_u : Ultimate fibre stress
 E_f : Fibre modulus

By analogy to the continuous fibre, we will apply the Pigott's model to the 3D composites. Thus, in this model, the bundle and woven Satin characteristic will replace respectively those of the mono-fibre and matrix.

The volume fraction of the bundle is defined by equation (4) :

$$V_{\text{bundle}} = \frac{\pi D^2}{4 p^2} \quad (4)$$

where :

D : bundle diameter = 0,52 mm (measured by microscopic observations)

P : stitch step

The bundle ultimate stress may be obtained from the basic characteristics:

$$\sigma_u = V_f \sigma_{uf} + \frac{V_m E_m \sigma_{uf}}{E_f} \quad (5)$$

E_m : epoxy modulus

E_f : bundle's fibre modulus

$$E_{bundle} = V_f E_f + V_m E_m \quad (6)$$

Then the energy is given by :

$$GI = \frac{\frac{p D^3}{4 p^2} [V_f s_{uf} + \frac{V_m E_m s_{uf}}{E_f}]^3}{6 (V_f E_f + V_m E_m) \tau_i} \quad (7)$$

This model was tested on the materials A, B2 and C. The fibre and matrix properties are given in the following table :

Materials	σ ultimate [GPa]	Young modulus [GPa]
T900	5,4	295
T300	3,5	230
Matrix	0,069	2,3

Table 2 : Mechanical properties of bundle constituents.

No value for the T900 / Epoxy interfacial stress was found in the literature, and a large range of the T300 / Epoxy (between 27,6 MPa to 48,7 Mpa) was found. We will then considered that interfacial failure occurred in the matrix around the fibre and then we will use the Tresca's criteria

$$\tau_i = \frac{\sigma_{um}}{2} = 30 \text{ MPa.} \quad \sigma_{um} : \text{Matrix ultimate stress}$$

The relation (7) shows that GI is particularly sensitive to the value of the stitch step. For this, ten microscopic measurements of different material's stitching step were performed.

The following table compares the different values of the energy obtained experimentally and by this model . There is a good correlation for the composites B2 and C, however the results of the model overestimat the interlaminar toughness of composite A by around 16 %.

References	GI experi. [J/m2]	GI model [J/m2]	Error %
A (T900 step = 5,12 mm)	5890 ± 250	7059	16
B2 (T900 step = 6,67 mm)	4690 ± 690	4159	11
C (T300 step = 5,02 mm)	2520 ± 420	2404	5

Table 3 : energy results obtained experimentally and theoretically.

Nevertheless, this model has the advantage to be simple to use, taking into account the geometry, the step and the mechanical properties of the stitching .

CONCLUSION

In this paper, a comparison of the energy strain release rate of four stitched composites materials has been carried out. The influence of the density and mechanical properties of the stitch was studied.

Without any specific method to calculate the strain energy release rate of these materials, an experimental methodology has been proposed to measure the interlaminar fracture energies at the stitch failure. This method is more adequate than the area method, especially, for the study of stitched composites loading rate effect which will be presented in future works.

The principal results are :

- The proximity of the stitch with respect to the crack tip provide an early damage which induce a lower "2D composite" fracture energy.
- The stitching step has an influence on the fracture energy. A difference of 2 mm in the step value can increase the fracture energy by 20 %.
- The mechanical properties of the stitch has also a great influence. Thus, the T900 graphite stitch provides an energy 56 % higher than the T300 graphite stitch.
- This study has shown that there is no effect of the thickness on the fracture energy values.
- The stitched composites offer values of Mode I energy 5 to 10 times greater than those of classical 2D composites.

Finally this work has proposed an adaptation of Pigott's model to predict the Mode I fracture energy. This model has the advantage to be simple to use, and it taking into account of structural and geometrical parameters of stitched composites.

A good correlation between experimental and theoretical results was observed.

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